

A Numerical Approach For The Algebra of Two-Fold 2×2 Fuzzy Real Matrices and Anti Fuzzy Matrices

Ahmad A. Abubaker^{*1}, Mayada Abualhomos², Khaled Matarneh³, Abdallah Al-Husban^{4,5}

¹Faculty of Computer Studies, Arab Open University, Saudi Arabia; a.abubaker@arabou.edu.sa

²Applied Science Private University Amman, 11931, Jordan; abuhomos@asu.edu.jo

³Faculty of Computer Studies, Arab Open University, Saudi Arabia; k.matarneh@arabou.edu.sa

⁴Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Technology, Irbid; National University, P.O. Box: 2600 Irbid, Jordan; dralhosban@inu.edu.jo

⁵Jadara Research Center, Jadara University, Irbid 21110, Jordan.

Abstract:

This paper is dedicated to study for the first time the concept of square 2×2 fuzzy and anti-fuzzy two-fold matrix with real entries, where we present the two-fold algebraic operations between the these matrices and obtain their special properties such as associativity, commutative properties, and the existing of additive of multiplicative inverses. Also, we provide many examples to explain the two-fold algebraic properties and the two-fold algebraic structure.

Keywords: two-fold algebra, two-fold real numbers, two-fold fuzzy matrix, two-fold inverse, anti-fuzzy matrix.

Introduction

The theory of matrices based on mathematical and algebraic logic has been studied by different authors around the world. For example, we can see many important results about the computations of plithogenic matrices in [5].

Also, neutrosophic matrices and their extended types have been defined and handled in [1-3], where many problems such as diagonalization, inverses, and algebraic representations were studied and provided [4, 6].

The two-fold algebra and two-fold algebraic structures began in [7], and then these algebras in fuzzy versions were used in many different contexts, such as mathematical analysis, algebraic elements, and in other types of mathematical structures [8-23].

In this paper we to study for the first time the concept of square 2×2 fuzzy and anti-fuzzy two-fold matrix with real entries, where we present the two-fold algebraic operations between the these matrices and obtain their special properties such as associativity, commutative properties, and the existing of additive of multiplicative inverses.

Two-Fold 2×2 -Fuzzy Real Matrices

Definition:

Let $\mathbb{R}$ be the real field, $\mu: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $\begin{cases} \mu(0) = 0 \\ \mu(1) = 1 \end{cases}$ be a fuzzy mapping. Let $\mathbb{R}_F = \{x_{\mu(y)} : x, y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ be the corresponding two-fold fuzzy real algebra, then we define:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1\mu(y_1)} & x_{2\mu(y_2)} \\ x_{3\mu(y_3)} & x_{4\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} ; x_i, y_i \in \mathbb{R}.$$

A is called a 2×2 fuzzy two-fold matrix.

Definition:

Let $a_i = (x_i)_{\mu(y_i)} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$, $b_i = (z_i)_{\mu(t_i)} \quad ; 1 \leq i \leq 4$ and $x_i, y_i, z_i, t_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $a_i, b_i \in \mathbb{R}_F$.

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix}$, $B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix}$, we define:

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 & a_2 * b_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 & a_4 * b_4 \end{pmatrix} ; a_i * b_i = (x_i + z_i)_{\min(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))}$$

$$-A = \begin{pmatrix} -a_1 & -a_2 \\ -a_3 & -a_4 \end{pmatrix} ; -a_i = (-x_i)_{\mu(-x_i)}$$

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where } a_i \circ b_j = (x_i z_j)_{\max(\mu(x_i), \mu(t_j))}$$

Example:S

$$\text{Take: } \mu: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0,1]: \mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x = 0 \\ 1 & ; x = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & ; x > 1 \\ \frac{1}{3} & ; x < 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} & ; 0 < x < 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{And: } a_1 = 3_{\mu(2)} = 3_{\frac{1}{2}}, a_2 = 4_{\mu(\frac{1}{3})} = 4_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$a_3 = 1_{\mu(-5)} = 1_{\frac{1}{3}}, a_4 = 0_{\mu(0)} = 0_0 ,$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 4_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ 1_{\frac{1}{3}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$b_1 = (-2)_{\mu(1)} = (-2)_1, b_2 = (-1)_{\mu(7)} = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}}, b_3 = (1)_{\mu(0)} = 1_0 ,$$

$$b_4 = (2)_{\mu(\frac{1}{10})} = 2_{\frac{1}{4}}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (-2)_1 & (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 1_0 & 2_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

We have:

$$-A = \begin{pmatrix} (-3)_{\mu(-2)} & (-4)_{\mu(\frac{-1}{3})} \\ (-1)_{\mu(5)} & (-0)_{\mu(-0)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (-3)_{\frac{1}{3}} & (-4)_{\frac{1}{3}} \\ (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 & a_2 * b_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 & a_4 * b_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_{\frac{1}{2}} & (3)_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ 2_0 & 2_0 \end{pmatrix}; \begin{cases} a_1 * b_1 = (3 - 2)_{\frac{1}{2}} = 1_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ a_2 * b_2 = (4 - 1)_{\frac{1}{4}} = 3_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ a_3 * b_3 = (1 + 1)_0 = 2_0 \\ a_4 * b_4 = (0 + 2)_0 = 2_0 \end{cases}$$

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} (-2)_{\frac{1}{4}} & 5_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ (-2)_0 & (-1)_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix}; \begin{cases} a_1 \circ b_1 = (-6)_1, a_2 \circ b_3 = 4_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) = (-2)_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ a_1 \circ b_2 = (-3)_{\frac{1}{2}}, a_2 \circ b_4 = 8_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) = 5_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{And: } \begin{cases} a_3 \circ b_1 = (-2)_1, a_4 \circ b_3 = (0)_0 \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) = (-2)_0 \\ a_3 \circ b_2 = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}}, a_4 \circ b_4 = 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) = (-1)_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Take } C = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & 0_1 \\ 1_0 & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ then:}$$

$$B \times C = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_1c_1 + b_2c_3 & b_1c_2 + b_2c_4 \\ b_3c_1 + b_4c_3 & b_3c_2 + b_4c_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$b_1c_1 = (-2)_1 \circ (1)_1 = (-2)_1, b_2c_3 = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} \circ (1_0) = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}}, b_1c_1 + b_2c_3 = (-2)_1 * (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} =$$

$$(-3)_{\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$b_1c_2 = (-2)_1 \circ (0)_1 = (0)_1, b_2c_4 = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} \circ (0)_0 = (0)_{\frac{1}{2}}, b_1c_2 + b_2c_4 = (0)_1 * (0)_{\frac{1}{2}} = (0)_{\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$b_3c_1 = (1_0) \circ (1_1) = (1_1), b_4c_3 = (2_{\frac{1}{4}}) \circ (1_0) = (2_{\frac{1}{4}}), b_3c_1 + b_4c_3 = (1_1) * (2_{\frac{1}{4}}) = (3_{\frac{1}{4}}),$$

$$b_3c_2 = (1_0) \circ (0_1) = (0_1), b_4c_4 = (2_{\frac{1}{4}}) \circ (0_0) = (0_{\frac{1}{4}}), b_3c_2 + b_4c_4 = (0_1) * (0_{\frac{1}{4}}) = (0_{\frac{1}{4}}),$$

$$\text{Thus } B \times C = \begin{pmatrix} -3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 0_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 3_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$A \times (B \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 4_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ 1_{\frac{1}{3}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} -3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 0_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 3_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ (-3)_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\left(3_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) \circ \left(-3_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(4_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ \left(3_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = \left(-9_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(12_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 3_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$\left(3_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) \circ \left(0_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(4_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = \left(0_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 0_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$\left(1_{\frac{1}{3}}\right) \circ \left(-3_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * (0_0) \circ \left(3_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = \left(-3_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = (-3)_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$\left(1_{\frac{1}{3}}\right) \circ \left(0_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * (0_0) \circ \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = \left(0_{\frac{1}{2}}\right) * \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 0_{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

$$(A \times B) \times C = \begin{pmatrix} -2_{\frac{1}{4}} & 5_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ -3_1 & -1_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & 0_1 \\ 1_0 & 0_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ -3_{\frac{1}{4}} & 0_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\left(-2_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (1_1) * \left(5_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (1_0) = (-2_1) * \left(5_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 3_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$\left(-2_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (0_1) * \left(5_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (0_0) = (0_1) * \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 0_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$(-2_1) \circ (1_1) * \left(-1_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (1_0) = (-2_1) * \left(-1_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = -3_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$(-3_1) \circ (0_1) * \left(-1_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) \circ (0_0) = (0_1) * \left(0_{\frac{1}{4}}\right) = 0_{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

Thus $(A \times B) \times C = A \times (B \times C)$.

$$B \times A = \begin{pmatrix} -2_1 & -1_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 1_0 & 2_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 4_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ 1_{\frac{1}{3}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -7_1 & m_1 \\ m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$(-2_1) \circ \left(\frac{3_1}{2}\right) * \left(-\frac{1_1}{2}\right) \circ \left(\frac{1_1}{3}\right) = (-6_1) * \left(-\frac{1_1}{2}\right) = -7_1$$

It is clear that $B \times A \neq A \times B$.

The Algebra Properties of two-fold Matrix Operations:

Property (1):

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix}; \begin{cases} a_i = (x_i)_{\mu(y_i)} & ; x_i, y_i \in \mathbb{R} \\ b_i = (z_i)_{\mu(t_i)} & ; z_i, t_i \in \mathbb{R} \end{cases}$

We have: $a_i * b_i = (x_i + z_i)_{\min(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))} = (z_i + x_i)_{\min(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))} = b_i * a_i$, then $A + B = B + A$.

Property (2):

Let $C = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix}; c_i = (m_i)_{\mu(n_i)}$, then:

$$B + C = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 * c_1 & b_2 * c_2 \\ b_3 * c_3 & b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix}, A + (B + C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 * c_1 & a_2 * b_2 * c_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 * c_3 & a_4 * b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix} = (A + B) + C.$$

Property (3):

$$A - A = A + (-A) = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} (-x_1)_{\mu(-y_1)} & (-x_2)_{\mu(-y_2)} \\ (-x_3)_{\mu(-y_3)} & (-x_4)_{\mu(-y_4)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0_{l_1} & 0_{l_2} \\ 0_{l_3} & 0_{l_4} \end{pmatrix};$$

$$l_i = \min(\mu(y_i), \mu(-y_i)).$$

Property (4):

$$A \times (B \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} (b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3) & (b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4) \\ (b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3) & (b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} d_1 & d_2 \\ d_3 & d_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ d_1) * (a_2 \circ d_3) & (a_1 \circ d_2) * (a_2 \circ d_4) \\ (a_3 \circ d_1) * (a_4 \circ d_3) & (a_3 \circ d_2) * (a_4 \circ d_4) \end{pmatrix}.$$

We have:

$$a_1 \circ d_1 = a_1 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3)] = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3), a_2 \circ d_3 = a_2 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3)] = (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

Put

$$T_1 = (a_1 \circ d_1) * (a_2 \circ d_3) = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3).$$

$$a_1 \circ d_2 = a_1 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4)] = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_4), a_2 \circ d_4 = a_2 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4)] = (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$T_2 = (a_1 \circ d_2) * (a_2 \circ d_4) = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_4) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$a_3 \circ d_1 = a_3 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3)] = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_3), a_4 \circ d_3 = a_4 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3)] = (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

Put

$$T_3 = (a_3 \circ d_1) * (a_4 \circ d_3) = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

$$a_3 \circ d_2 = a_3 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4)] = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_4), a_4 \circ d_4 = a_4 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4)] = (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$T_4 = (a_3 \circ d_2) * (a_4 \circ d_4) = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_4) * (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_4).$$

$$\text{Thus } A \times (B \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} T_1 & T_2 \\ T_3 & T_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$(A \times B) \times C = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} k_1 & k_2 \\ k_3 & k_4 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where}$$

$$k_1 = [(a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3)] \circ c_1 * [(a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4)] \circ c_3 = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3) = T_1.$$

By a similar argument, we can see clearly that:

$$k_2 = T_2, k_3 = T_3, k_4 = T_4, \text{ thus } A \times (B \times C) = (A \times B) \times C.$$

Property (5):

$$A \times (B + C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} b_1 * c_1 & b_2 * c_2 \\ b_3 * c_3 & b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} F_1 & F_2 \\ F_3 & F_4 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where:}$$

$$F_1 = a_1 \circ (b_1 * c_1) * a_2 \circ (b_3 * c_3) = (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) * (a_2 \circ c_3),$$

$$F_2 = a_1 \circ (b_2 * c_3) * a_2 \circ (b_4 * c_4) = (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_1 \circ c_3) * (a_2 \circ b_4) * (a_2 \circ c_4),$$

$$F_3 = a_3 \circ (b_1 * c_1) * a_4 \circ (b_3 * c_3) = (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) * (a_4 \circ c_3),$$

$$F_4 = a_3 \circ (b_2 * c_2) * a_4 \circ (b_4 * c_4) = (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) * (a_4 \circ c_4),$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$(A \times B) + (A \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix} +$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ c_3) & (a_1 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ c_4) \\ (a_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ c_3) & (a_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ c_4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} F_1 & F_2 \\ F_3 & F_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Which implies that $A \times (B + C) = (A \times B) + (A \times C)$.

Result:

If TF_μ is the set of all (2×2) two-fold fuzzy matrices with two-fold real entries, then:

- 1] (+) is a commutative and associative.
- 2] ($\times$) is associative.
- 3] ($\times$) is a distributive with respect to (+).

Definition:

A (2×2) two-fold zero fuzzy matrix is defined as:

$$O = \begin{pmatrix} 0_1 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & 0_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Remark:

For any $A \in TF_\mu$, we have $A + O = O + A = A$.

It is clear that $A \times O = O$.

The additive inverse of $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix}$ is not existed.

Definition:

A (2×2) two-fold unitary matrix is:

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1_0 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & 1_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Remark:

For $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix}$, we have:

$$A \times I = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} 1_0 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & 1_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} L_1 & L_2 \\ L_3 & L_4 \end{pmatrix};$$

$$L_1 = ((x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ 1_0) * ((x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ 0_1) = (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} * (0_1) = (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)}$$

$$L_2 = ((x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ 0_1) * ((x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ 1_0) = (0_1) * (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} = (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)}$$

$$L_3 = (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)}, L_4 = (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)},$$

thus $A \times I = I \times A = A$.

Finding the multiplicative inverse:

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} \in TF_\mu$; $x_1x_4 - x_2x_3 \neq 0$

Put $B = \begin{pmatrix} (x_4)_{\mu(z_4)} & (-x_2)_{\mu(z_2)} \\ (-x_3)_{\mu(z_3)} & (x_1)_{\mu(z_1)} \end{pmatrix}$, and compute:

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & \mu_2 \\ \mu_3 & \mu_4 \end{pmatrix} \text{ such that:}$$

$$\mu_1 = [(x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ (x_4)_{\mu(z_4)}] * [(x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ (-x_3)_{\mu(z_3)}] = (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_{l_1};$$

$$l_1 = \min[\max(\mu(y_1), \mu(z_4)), \max(\mu(y_2), \mu(z_3))] = 1,$$

Thus: we can put: $\mu(z_4) = \mu(z_3) = 1$.

Also, if we put $\mu(z_2) = \mu(z_1) = 1$, then:

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Define:

$\det A = (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1$, then:

$$\frac{1}{(x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1} \times \begin{pmatrix} (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & 0_1 \\ 0_1 & 1_1 \end{pmatrix} \neq I.$$

On the other hand, if we put $l_1 = 0$, then we can not choose $\mu(z_4), \mu(z_3)$ to obtain this result, which means that A is not invertible.

Result:

The set of all two-fold fuzzy matrices is not a ring, that is because there are no additive inverses.

Two-Fold 2×2 anti-Fuzzy Real Matrices:

Definition:

Let $\mathbb{R}$ be the real field, $\mu: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $\begin{cases} \mu(0) = 0 \\ \mu(1) = 1 \end{cases}$ be a fuzzy mapping. Let $\mathbb{R}_F = \{x_{\mu(y)} : x, y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ be the corresponding two-fold fuzzy real algebra, then we define:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1\mu(y_1)} & x_{2\mu(y_2)} \\ x_{3\mu(y_3)} & x_{4\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} ; x_i, y_i \in \mathbb{R}.$$

A is called a 2×2 anti-fuzzy two-fold matrix.

Definition:

Let $a_i = (x_i)_{\mu(y_i)} \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$, $b_i = (z_i)_{\mu(t_i)} \quad ; 1 \leq i \leq 4$ and $x_i, y_i, z_i, t_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $a_i, b_i \in \mathbb{R}_F$.

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix}$, $B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix}$, we define:

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 & a_2 * b_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 & a_4 * b_4 \end{pmatrix} ; a_i * b_i = (x_i + z_i)_{\max(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))}$$

$$-A = \begin{pmatrix} -a_1 & -a_2 \\ -a_3 & -a_4 \end{pmatrix} ; -a_i = (-x_i)_{\mu(-x_i)}$$

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where } a_i \circ b_j = (x_i z_j)_{\min(\mu(x_i), \mu(t_j))}$$

Example:

$$\text{Take: } \mu: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0,1]: \mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x = 0 \\ 1 & ; x = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & ; x > 1 \\ \frac{1}{3} & ; x < 0 \\ \frac{1}{4} & ; 0 < x < 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{And: } a_1 = 3_{\mu(2)} = 3_{\frac{1}{2}}, a_2 = 4_{\mu(\frac{1}{3})} = 4_{\frac{1}{4}},$$

$$a_3 = 1_{\mu(-5)} = 1_{\frac{1}{3}}, a_4 = 0_{\mu(0)} = 0_0 ,$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 3_{\frac{1}{2}} & 4_{\frac{1}{4}} \\ 1_{\frac{1}{3}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$b_1 = (-2)_{\mu(1)} = (-2)_1, b_2 = (-1)_{\mu(7)} = (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}}, b_3 = (1)_{\mu(0)} = 1_0 ,$$

$$b_4 = (2)_{\mu(\frac{1}{10})} = 2_{\frac{1}{4}}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (-2)_1 & (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 1_0 & 2_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

We have:

$$-A = \begin{pmatrix} (-3)_{\mu(-2)} & (-4)_{\mu(\frac{-1}{3})} \\ (-1)_{\mu(5)} & (-0)_{\mu(-0)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (-3)_{\frac{1}{3}} & (-4)_{\frac{1}{3}} \\ (-1)_{\frac{1}{2}} & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$A + B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 & a_2 * b_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 & a_4 * b_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & (3)_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ 2_{\frac{1}{3}} & 2_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{pmatrix}; \begin{cases} a_1 * b_1 = (3 - 2)_1 = 1_1 \\ a_2 * b_2 = (4 - 1)_{\frac{1}{2}} = 3_{\frac{1}{2}} \\ a_3 * b_3 = (1 + 1)_{\frac{1}{3}} = 2_{\frac{1}{3}} \\ a_4 * b_4 = (0 + 2)_{\frac{1}{4}} = 2_{\frac{1}{4}} \end{cases}$$

The Algebraic Properties of two-fold anti-fuzzy Matrix Operations:

Property (1):

$$\text{Let } A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 & b_2 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix}; \begin{cases} a_i = (x_i)_{\mu(y_i)} & ; x_i, y_i \in \mathbb{R} \\ b_i = (z_i)_{\mu(t_i)} & ; z_i, t_i \in \mathbb{R} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{We have: } a_i * b_i = (x_i + z_i)_{\max(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))} = (z_i + x_i)_{\max(\mu(y_i), \mu(t_i))} = b_i * a_i,$$

then $A + B = B + A$.

Property (2):

$$\text{Let } C = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix}; c_i = (m_i)_{\mu(n_i)}, \text{ then:}$$

$$B + C = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 * c_1 & b_2 * c_2 \\ b_3 * c_3 & b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix}, A + (B + C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * b_1 * c_1 & a_2 * b_2 * c_2 \\ a_3 * b_3 * c_3 & a_4 * b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix} = (A + B) + C.$$

Property (3):

$$A - A = A + (-A) = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} (-x_1)_{\mu(-y_1)} & (-x_2)_{\mu(-y_2)} \\ (-x_3)_{\mu(-y_3)} & (-x_4)_{\mu(-y_4)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0_{l_1} & 0_{l_2} \\ 0_{l_3} & 0_{l_4} \end{pmatrix};$$

$$l_i = \max(\mu(y_i), \mu(-y_i)).$$

Property (4):

$$A \times (B \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} (b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3) & (b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4) \\ (b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3) & (b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} d_1 & d_2 \\ d_3 & d_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ d_1) * (a_2 \circ d_3) & (a_1 \circ d_2) * (a_2 \circ d_4) \\ (a_3 \circ d_1) * (a_4 \circ d_3) & (a_3 \circ d_2) * (a_4 \circ d_4) \end{pmatrix}.$$

We have:

$$a_1 \circ d_1 = a_1 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3)] = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3), a_2 \circ d_3 = a_2 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3)] = (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

Put

$$T_1 = (a_1 \circ d_1) * (a_2 \circ d_3) = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3).$$

$$a_1 \circ d_2 = a_1 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4)] = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_4), a_2 \circ d_4 = a_2 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4)] = (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$T_2 = (a_1 \circ d_2) * (a_2 \circ d_4) = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_4) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$a_3 \circ d_1 = a_3 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_1) * (b_2 \circ c_3)] = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_3), a_4 \circ d_3 = a_4 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_1) * (b_4 \circ c_3)] = (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

Put

$$T_3 = (a_3 \circ d_1) * (a_4 \circ d_3) = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_3),$$

$$a_3 \circ d_2 = a_3 \circ [(b_1 \circ c_2) * (b_2 \circ c_4)] = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_4), a_4 \circ d_4 = a_4 \circ [(b_3 \circ c_2) * (b_4 \circ c_4)] = (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_4),$$

$$T_4 = (a_3 \circ d_2) * (a_4 \circ d_4) = (a_3 \circ b_1 \circ c_2) * (a_3 \circ b_2 \circ c_4) * (a_4 \circ b_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4 \circ c_4).$$

$$\text{Thus } A \times (B \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} T_1 & T_2 \\ T_3 & T_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$(A \times B) \times C = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} c_1 & c_2 \\ c_3 & c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} k_1 & k_2 \\ k_3 & k_4 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where}$$

$$k_1 = [(a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3)] \circ c_1 * [(a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4)] \circ c_3 = (a_1 \circ b_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3 \circ c_1) * (a_1 \circ b_2 \circ c_3) * (a_2 \circ b_4 \circ c_3) = T_1.$$

By a similar argument, we can see clearly that:

$$k_2 = T_2, k_3 = T_3, k_4 = T_4, \text{ thus } A \times (B \times C) = (A \times B) \times C.$$

Property (5):

$$A \times (B + C) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} b_1 * c_1 & b_2 * c_2 \\ b_3 * c_3 & b_4 * c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} F_1 & F_2 \\ F_3 & F_4 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ where:}$$

$$F_1 = a_1 \circ (b_1 * c_1) * a_2 \circ (b_3 * c_3) = (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) * (a_2 \circ c_3),$$

$$F_2 = a_1 \circ (b_2 * c_2) * a_2 \circ (b_4 * c_4) = (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_1 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) * (a_2 \circ c_4),$$

$$F_3 = a_3 \circ (b_1 * c_1) * a_4 \circ (b_3 * c_3) = (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) * (a_4 \circ c_3),$$

$$F_4 = a_3 \circ (b_2 * c_2) * a_4 \circ (b_4 * c_4) = (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) * (a_4 \circ c_4),$$

On the other hand, we have:

$$(A \times B) + (A \times C) = \begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ b_1) * (a_2 \circ b_3) & (a_1 \circ b_2) * (a_2 \circ b_4) \\ (a_3 \circ b_1) * (a_4 \circ b_3) & (a_3 \circ b_2) * (a_4 \circ b_4) \end{pmatrix} +$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} (a_1 \circ c_1) * (a_2 \circ c_3) & (a_1 \circ c_2) * (a_2 \circ c_4) \\ (a_3 \circ c_1) * (a_4 \circ c_3) & (a_3 \circ c_2) * (a_4 \circ c_4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} F_1 & F_2 \\ F_3 & F_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Which implies that $A \times (B + C) = (A \times B) + (A \times C)$.

Result:

If TF_μ is the set of all (2×2) two-fold anti- fuzzy matrices with two-fold real entries, then:

- 1] $(+)$ is a commutative and associative.
- 2] $(\times)$ is associative.
- 3] $(\times)$ is a distributive with respect to $(+)$.

Definition:

A (2×2) two-fold zero anti- fuzzy matrix is defined as:

$$O = \begin{pmatrix} 0_0 & 0_0 \\ 0_0 & 0_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Remark:

For any $A \in TF_\mu$, we have $A + O = O + A = A$.

It is clear that $A \times O = O$.

The additive inverse of $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix}$ is not existed.

Definition:

A (2×2) two-fold anti-fuzzy unitary matrix is:

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & 0_0 \\ 0_0 & 1_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Remark:

For $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix}$, we have:

$$A \times I = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 & 0_0 \\ 0_0 & 1_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} L_1 & L_2 \\ L_3 & L_4 \end{pmatrix};$$

$$L_1 = ((x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ 1_1) * ((x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ 0_0) = (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} * (0_0) = (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)}$$

$$L_2 = ((x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ 0_0) * ((x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ 1_1) = (0_0) * (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} = (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)}$$

$$L_3 = (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)}, L_4 = (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)},$$

thus $A \times I = I \times A = A$.

Finding the multiplicative inverse:

Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} (x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} & (x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \\ (x_3)_{\mu(y_3)} & (x_4)_{\mu(y_4)} \end{pmatrix} \in TF_{\mu} ; x_1x_4 - x_2x_3 \neq 0$

Put $B = \begin{pmatrix} (x_4)_{\mu(z_4)} & (-x_2)_{\mu(z_2)} \\ (-x_3)_{\mu(z_3)} & (x_1)_{\mu(z_1)} \end{pmatrix}$, and compute:

$$A \times B = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & \mu_2 \\ \mu_3 & \mu_4 \end{pmatrix} \text{ such that:}$$

$$\mu_1 = [(x_1)_{\mu(y_1)} \circ (x_4)_{\mu(z_4)}] * [(x_2)_{\mu(y_2)} \circ (-x_3)_{\mu(z_3)}] = (x_1x_4 - x_2x_3)_{l_1};$$

$$l_1 = \max[\min(\mu(y_1), \mu(z_4)), \min(\mu(y_2), \mu(z_3))] = 1,$$

We can not get a similar result by choosing $\mu(z_3), \mu(z_4)$

which means that A is not invertible.

Conclusion

In this paper we have studied for the first time the concept of square 2×2 fuzzy and anti-fuzzy two-fold matrix with real entries, where we presented the two-fold algebraic operations between the these matrices and obtain their special properties such as

associativity, commutative properties, and the existing of additive of multiplicative inverses. Also, we provided many examples to explain the two-fold algebraic properties and the two-fold algebraic structure.

References

1. Abobala, M., On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications In Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations, Journal Of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021
2. Olgun, N., Hatip, A., Bal, M., and Abobala, M., " A Novel Approach To Necessary and Sufficient Conditions For The Diagonalization of Refined Neutrosophic Matrices", International Journal of neutrosophic Science, Vol. 16, pp. 72-79, 2021.
3. Abobala, M., Hatip, A., and Bal, M., " A Review On Recent Advantages In Algebraic Theory Of Neutrosophic Matrices", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol.17, 2021.
4. Abobala, M., Ziena, B,M., Doewes, R., and Hussein, Z., "The Representation Of Refined Neutrosophic Matrices By Refined Neutrosophic Linear Functions", International Journal Of Neutrosophic Science, 2022.
5. Ben Othman, K., Von Shtawzen, O., Khaldi, A., and Ali, R., "On The Symbolic 8-Plithogenic Matrices", Pure Mathematics For Theoretical Computer Science, Vol.1, 2023.
6. Abobala, M., On The Representation of Neutrosophic Matrices by Neutrosophic Linear Transformations, Journal of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021.
7. Florentine Smarandache. "Neutrosophic Two-Fold Algebra", Plithogenic Logic and Computation, Vol.1, No.1 2024. PP.11-15.
8. Mohammad Abobala. (2023). On a Two-Fold Algebra Based on the Standard Fuzzy Number Theoretical System. Journal of Neutrosophic and Fuzzy Systems, 7 (2), 24-29
(Doi : <https://doi.org/10.54216/JNFS.070202>).
9. Ahmed Hatip, Necati Olgun. (2023). On the Concepts of Two- Fold Fuzzy Vector Spaces and Algebraic Modules. Journal of Neutrosophic and Fuzzy Systems, 7 (2), 46-52
(Doi : <https://doi.org/10.54216/JNFS.070205>).

10. Ramazan Yasar, and Ahmed Hatip, The Structure of The Binary Two Fold Algebra Based On Intuitionistic Fuzzy Groups, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 72, 2024, pp. 134-141, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13381912.
11. A. S. Heilat, H. Zureigat, R. Hatamleh, B. Batiha, New Spline Method for Solving Linear Two-Point Boundary Value Problems. *European Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 14 (4), 1283-1294, 2021
12. Al-Husban, A. B. D. U. L. L. A. H., Al-Sharoa, D. O. A. A., Al-Kaseasbeh, M. O. H. A. M. M. A. D., & Mahmood, R. M. S. (2022). Structures of fibers of groups actions on graphs. *WSEAS Trans. Math*, 7, 650-658.
13. Al-Husban, a. b. d. a. l. l. a. h., al-sharoa, d. o. a. a., saadeh, r., qazza, a., & mahmood, r. (2023). On the fibers of the tree products of groups with amalgamation subgroups. *Journal of applied mathematics & informatics*, 41(6), 1237-1256.
14. Al-Shbeil, Isra. , Abu, Ibraheem. , Alkhouli, Talat. , Soiman, Ahmed. , Shtayat, Jenan. , Al-Husban, Abdallah. On the Two-Fold Maximal Units in Some Two-Fold Finite Neutrosophic Rings Modulo Integers for $2 \leq n \leq 5$. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, vol. , no. , 2025, pp. 155-164. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.250213>
15. Shihadeh, A., Matarneh, K. A. M., Hatamleh, R., Al-Qadri, M. O., & Al-Husban, A. (2024). On The Two-Fold Fuzzy n-Refined Neutrosophic Rings For $2 \leq n \leq 3$. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 68, 8-25.
16. Abdallah Shihadeh, Khaled Ahmad Mohammad Matarneh, Raed Hatamleh, Randa Bashir Yousef Hijazeen, Mowafaq Omar Al-Qadri, Abdallah Al-Husban. (2024). An Example of Two-Fold Fuzzy Algebras Based On Neutrosophic Real Numbers, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 67.
17. C. Sivakumar, Mowafaq Omar Al-Qadri, Abdallah shihadeh, Ahmed Atallah Alsaraireh, Abdallah Al-Husban, P. Maragatha Meenakshi, N. Rajesh, M. Palanikumar. (2024). q-rung square root interval-valued neutrosophic sets with respect to aggregated operators using multiple attribute decision making. *Journal of* , 23 (3), 154-174 (Doi : <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.230314>)
18. Selvaraj, S., Gharib, G., Al-Husban, A., Al Soudi, M., Kumaran, K. L. M., Palanikumar, M., & Sundareswari, K. New algebraic approach towards interval-valued neutrosophic cubic vague set based on subbisemiring over bisemiring. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 23(4), 386-394.
19. Falahah, I. A., Raman, T. T., Al-Husban, A., Alahmade, A., Azhaguvelavan, S., & Palanikumar, M. (2024) Computer purchasing using new type neutrosophic sets

- and its extension based on aggregation operators. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 23(4), 386-394.
20. A.Abubaker, Ahmad. , M., Wael. , Alrawashdeh, Heba. , Shatarah, Amani. , Mousa, Norah. , Al-Husban, Abdallah. The Mathematical Formulas for Inverting Plithogenic Matrices of Special Orders Between 20 and 24. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, vol. , no. , 2024, pp. 102-114. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.240309>.
 21. Abu, Ibraheem. , Al-Husban, Abdallah. , M., Mutaz. , A., Ahmed. , Shatarah, Amani. , Mousa, Norah. On the Characterization of Some m-Plithogenic Vector Spaces and Their AH-Substructures Under the Condition $6 \leq \dim SPV \leq 10$. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, vol.24 , no. 3, 2024, pp. 258-267. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.240322>.
 22. Isra Al-Shbeil, Wael Mahmoud M. Salameh, Hossam Almahasneh, Khalid Kaabneh, Mutaz Shatnawi, Khaled Al-Husban. (2024). Algorithms for Computing M-Plithogenic Eigen Values and Vectors for Some Special Values of M. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 24 (1), 128-135 (Doi : <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.240112>).
 23. Raed Hatamleh, Ayman Hazaymeh.(2024). Finding Minimal Units In Several Two-Fold Fuzzy Finite Neutrosophic Rings, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*,70,1-16.(DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13160839).

Acknowledgments

The authors extend their appreciation to the Arab Open University for funding this work through AOU research fund no. (AOUKSA-524008).

Received: June 1, 2024. Accepted: Oct 12, 2024